

AN OVERVIEW OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE THERAPIES AND THEIR CLINICAL LIMITATIONS

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Introduction

Neurodegenerative diseases (NDs) represent a growing global health challenge, driven by an aging population, modern lifestyle factors, increasing prevalence, and the substantial physical, emotional, and financial burdens placed on patients, caregivers, and healthcare systems. Currently, over 50 million individuals worldwide are affected by NDs, and this figure is projected to nearly triple to 152 million by 2050 if no effective preventive or therapeutic measures are developed. Among these disorders, Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most prevalent, accounting for approximately 60% to 80% of all neurodegenerative cases.

First described in 1907, Alzheimer's disease is multifactorial in origin, though its precise causes remain unclear. More than a century later, no curative treatment exists. AD presents in two primary forms: (1) autosomal-dominant Alzheimer's disease (ADAD), a rare hereditary form manifesting before age 65 and accounting for less than 1% of cases; and (2) the more common sporadic Alzheimer's disease (SAD), typically occurring after the age of 65, with the risk doubling every five years thereafter. This review focuses on the sporadic form of AD.

The pathology of AD involves both structural and functional deterioration of the central nervous system (CNS), primarily characterized by abnormal protein aggregation and progressive neurodegeneration. Two hallmark lesions are commonly observed: extracellular amyloid plaques composed of beta-amyloid ($A\beta$) peptides, and intracellular neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) formed by hyperphosphorylated tau protein. These pathological changes contribute to a cascade of biochemical, neurophysiological, neuroanatomical, and cognitive impairments, with initial damage manifesting at the synaptic level due to soluble $A\beta$ oligomers.

Over the past decade, research has increasingly focused on soluble $A\beta$ oligomers ($A\beta$ Os), as they appear to be more neurotoxic and closely associated with disease progression than insoluble plaques. These oligomers can cause early synaptic dysfunction before the appearance of classical neuropathological signs, leading eventually to neuronal loss in specific brain regions. In the early stages, this damage may occur without clinical symptoms, but over time, it results in progressive memory loss and cognitive decline.

Although numerous therapeutic strategies have been investigated through clinical trials, current treatments offer only symptomatic relief rather than addressing the underlying disease process. As a result, greater emphasis is now placed on prevention and risk reduction. Evidence suggests that more than 30% of AD cases could be attributed to modifiable risk factors, presenting promising opportunities for preventive interventions aimed at slowing cognitive decline and reducing overall disease burden.

Clinical description

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is recognized as a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that evolves over several years, with a gradual onset of cognitive impairment. It is marked by a steady decline in multiple cognitive domains, most notably memory—particularly in acquiring

and retrieving new information. Over time, additional cognitive impairments may emerge, including language disturbances (aphasia), impaired motor planning (apraxia), difficulties in object recognition (agnosia), and executive dysfunction. Clinically, AD is often classified as an amnesic syndrome of the hippocampal type. These neuropsychological deficits progressively interfere with daily living activities, reflecting a significant cognitive and functional decline relative to the individual's previous abilities.

In recent years, increasing attention has been directed toward the neuropsychiatric and behavioral aspects of AD. Common manifestations include psychotic features, depressive symptoms, apathy, irritability or aggression, and sleep disturbances. In response to the prevalence and impact of these symptoms, the International Psychogeriatric Association introduced the concept of behavioral and psychological symptoms of dementia (BPSD) in 1996, encompassing disturbances in perception, thought content, mood, and behavior frequently observed in individuals with neurodegenerative diseases.

Pathophysiology

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is characterized by extensive structural and functional degeneration within the central nervous system (CNS). Two hallmark histopathological features define its etiology: amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs). NFTs initially form in the inner regions of the temporal lobe, particularly the hippocampus, and can be present even in individuals who do not yet show clinical signs of cognitive decline. As the disease progresses, these tangles extend outward to the lateral temporal lobe, and subsequently spread to the posterior associative cortical areas and, eventually, throughout the cerebral cortex. This spatial progression closely mirrors the clinical evolution of AD symptoms.

In contrast, amyloid plaques exhibit a more widespread distribution. They first appear in the neocortex, then progressively involve the hippocampus, subcortical nuclei, and finally the cerebellum. These plaques are formed by the extracellular accumulation of beta-amyloid ($A\beta$) peptides, which are generated through the amyloidogenic processing of amyloid precursor protein (APP) by β - and γ -secretases.

Soluble $A\beta$ oligomers are considered especially neurotoxic. These oligomers may disrupt neuronal function either through direct interaction with neuronal membranes or by binding to specific receptors. Such interactions impair intracellular signaling pathways, alter neuronal activity, and activate microglial cells, leading to the release of neurotoxic mediators. These early events result in synaptic dysfunction, compromised axonal transport, and disturbances in neural plasticity.

Moreover, the presence of soluble $A\beta$ oligomers is linked to a cascade of pathological processes including oxidative stress, insulin resistance, tau protein hyperphosphorylation, cholinergic system disruption, and selective neuronal loss. Additional contributing factors include dysregulation of lipid and glucose metabolism, chronic neuroinflammation, cerebrovascular impairment, and dysfunction of the endosomal-lysosomal pathways. Vascular abnormalities can further exacerbate AD pathology by reducing cerebral blood flow, impairing nutrient delivery, and hampering the clearance of metabolic waste, ultimately promoting persistent inflammation via astrocyte and microglial activation.

Diagnostic Criteria for AD

The diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease (AD) has evolved significantly over the years. Initially, the criteria published in 1984 by the National Institute on Neurological and

Communicative Disorders and Stroke and the Alzheimer's Disease and Related Disorders Association were based predominantly on clinical and pathological features, especially memory impairment. However, these early criteria did not fully account for the variability in clinical presentations. Some individuals may show biomarker evidence of AD without cognitive decline, while others may display cognitive symptoms in the absence of biomarker confirmation.

In 2011, the National Institute on Aging and the Alzheimer's Association (NIA-AA) updated the diagnostic framework to include both mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and AD, incorporating clinical, cognitive, and functional assessments. The most common MCI subtype linked to AD is amnesic MCI (aMCI), which can affect either a single domain or multiple cognitive domains. aMCI is often considered a prodromal stage of AD, where memory function is significantly reduced compared to age, gender, and educational norms. However, these deficits are not severe enough to meet the criteria for dementia. The diagnosis of AD can be made in the absence of dementia if additional features are present, such as amnesic hippocampal syndrome or positive AD-specific biomarkers.

Specific AD Biomarkers

Both the NIA-AA and the International Working Group (IWG) conceptualize AD as a continuum that progresses slowly over time, beginning well before the appearance of clinical symptoms. This continuum consists of three stages: a preclinical (asymptomatic) phase, a prodromal phase represented by MCI due to AD, and a final stage of dementia due to AD.

Although clinical evaluation remains central to diagnosis, biomarker evidence is increasingly essential for confirming AD pathology. Modern diagnostic protocols include cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) biomarkers—such as total Tau, phosphorylated Tau, and A β 42 or the A β 42/A β 40 ratio—as well as neuroimaging techniques like positron emission tomography (PET) for visualizing Tau and amyloid deposits. These tests help classify the likelihood (high, intermediate, or low) that the observed cognitive symptoms are due to AD-related neurodegeneration.

In 2018, a new biological framework was proposed to define AD based on a sequential model of biomarker changes, which precede clinical symptoms by several years. According to this framework, AD is marked by a progressive cascade of neurophysiological, biochemical, and structural brain alterations.

The pathological hallmarks of AD remain the abnormal accumulation of amyloid-beta (A β) and Tau proteins. These features not only support diagnosis but also help differentiate AD from other neurodegenerative diseases. Biomarkers of amyloid pathology include reduced A β 1-42 levels in CSF or elevated amyloid uptake in PET scans. Tau pathology is confirmed by elevated CSF levels of total and phosphorylated Tau, or through Tau PET imaging.

Drug Treatments

Description

Current pharmacological treatments for Alzheimer's disease (AD) are designed to manage symptoms rather than cure the condition. These therapies primarily aim to slow cognitive decline and alleviate behavioral and psychological symptoms of dementia (BPSD). At present, four drugs—donepezil, memantine, galantamine, and rivastigmine—are approved for clinical use. They fall into two main classes: anticholinesterase inhibitors and anti-glutamatergic agents. These medications are administered either orally or via transdermal patches.

Anticholinesterase inhibitors work by increasing the concentration of acetylcholine in the brain—a neurotransmitter involved in memory and communication between neurons. These drugs aim to counteract the acetylcholine deficiency commonly observed in the central nervous system (CNS) of AD patients. Anti-glutamatergic agents, on the other hand, regulate glutamate levels by acting as non-competitive antagonists of N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors. Glutamate plays a crucial role in learning and memory, but excessive levels can lead to excitotoxicity and neuronal death.

Although these treatments do not halt disease progression, they may delay cognitive deterioration, provide temporary stabilization or improvement in memory and behavior, and support greater patient independence. They can also contribute to improving the quality of life for both patients and caregivers. However, their therapeutic effects are modest and temporary, as they address only the symptoms and not the root cause of the disease.

These drugs tend to be more effective when administered during the early, preclinical stages of AD, before significant neurodegeneration has occurred. One of the key barriers to their effectiveness is the difficulty of delivering drugs across the blood–brain barrier (BBB), which restricts access to the CNS. Due to poor BBB permeability, higher doses are often required, increasing the risk of adverse side effects. Consequently, various drug delivery strategies have been developed to enhance brain targeting and improve therapeutic outcomes.

Additionally, drug effectiveness can be compromised by age-related changes in neuronal membranes and receptor function, which are often not accounted for in preclinical research. Recent studies in aged mouse models have revealed changes in synaptosomal microdomains that increase vulnerability to amyloid-induced stress and reduce responsiveness to neuroprotective agents such as ciliary neurotrophic factor.

Another challenge is that treatments are frequently administered at advanced stages of AD, by which time neuronal damage is extensive and less reversible. For example, preclinical studies using mouse models with early-onset AD-related genetic mutations have demonstrated that immunotherapies can reduce amyloid plaque accumulation. However, in human clinical trials, similar anti-amyloid approaches showed a decrease in amyloid burden without corresponding clinical improvement or disease slowing, suggesting that these treatments may be introduced too late to be effective.

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